

COGNITIVE FUNDAMENTALS OF DEVELOPING THE MUSICAL TALENT OF STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF SPECIALIZED EDUCATION

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Abstract. *In this article, the cognitive foundations of the development of students' musical talent in the process of specialized education are analyzed with the opinions of world scientists.*

Keywords: *talent, generative music, artificial intelligence, scientific progress, phenomenon, sensitivity, musical sensitivity, motor reactions to musical rhythm, conception, motivation.*

Introduction: Today, our talented young people, or children who are interested in other music, do not learn the art of music by playing a couple of tunes and 'navos' with musical instruments, but by knowing the meaning of the music they are performing, the meaning of the song they are performing. We hope that scientific information will serve to a certain extent for the compatibility of his music with him and for his correct understanding. Because in the formation of a person as a person, the activities of young people who strive for greatness take place as a result of the improvement of their first interests and the abilities that have arisen through them.

"All of you are witnesses, these days debates about generative music and artificial intelligence are getting heated. Predictions are made that only technology will create the music of the future. But we all know very well that any perfect technical tool can never suppress the breath of a living person, the moans of his heart, the charm of a living voice, the place of true art" [1] - the words of President Sh.M.Mirziyoev will be imprinted in our memory. At the heart of this idea, we can see that there is a lack of a cognitive approach to music literacy today and that it is necessary to develop the musical talent of specialized schoolchildren.

Therefore, in "a systematic process aimed at providing students with in-depth theoretical knowledge, skills and practical skills, as well as forming their general and professional knowledge, skills and abilities, and developing their abilities" [2], the invaluable musical heritage left by our ancestors. A cognitive approach is necessary in order to deeply study its meaning, and most importantly, to feel the feelings and inner forgiveness of our classic music and their creators.

Main part: On the basis of the development of science, not only the improvement of musical literacy of students, but also the general worldview, inner world, spirituality and upbringing of a person should be the main factor. Because through musical literacy, one can see the essence of the philosophical and educational processes that are reflected as a form of the artistic culture of the owner of intelligence. Music education today is recognized by scientists as a system that combines educational criteria. For example, E.B. Abdullin said that the content of music education is a problem that encompasses all aspects of educational processes, and he said that "The

main focus is on the personality and activity of the student, the music teacher and their interaction with the art of music. "directed to the secret" [3] he emphasizes.

Modern music education is distinguished by the study of the possibilities of art and pedagogy, that is, the interpretation of the priority qualities of a talented student who is interested in music, and the discovery of the features of the art of music in human life. The meaning, types and achievements of music, its role in human life are taken into account. In the socio-economic conditions of the development of the society, studying the musical talent of students has become one of the continuous priorities aimed not only at high professional efficiency, but also at self-development, recognized by world scientists. But some of them have the opinion that "the insufficient scientific development of the single theoretical concept of musical talent, the lack of a single opinion of researchers on the diagnosis, definition and development of musical talent complicates the process of studying this problem" [4]. This, in turn, requires a psychological study of the phenomenon of talent in the science of music, the identification of its components, and the mastery of several concepts.

In fact, if we look at the sources, "The peculiarity of musical talent, which distinguishes it from other types of art, is the presence of musical ability, which is expressed by the individual's special inclination to listen to music and the increase in sensitivity to it" [5] - attention is paid to its features. And "Emotional sensitivity to music, musical sensitivity and activity, motor reactions to musical rhythm, preference of one piece of music over another, attempts to sing" [6]¹ we can find explanations of the musical talent that appears in the early years of life. It is also recommended that parents notice the first musical talent in childhood, and take family action in its development. According to scientific sources, "Musical talent is a multi-component concept... The first and leading pedagogical condition for the successful development of musical talent is the improvement of their musical and creative activities and the development of various musical knowledge, skills and abilities of this main task. "It is necessary to pay attention to academic work" [7]. "Musical talent - says Anisa Arsic in her article - is developed through the systematic monitoring and stimulation of other types of talent, so that talented individuals can acquire competencies that allow them to direct their abilities to creative and highly effective work." [8]. So, starting the development of musical talent in students according to their age, it becomes clear that they can express their musical abilities by increasing their love for music, along with the increase in their musical literacy.

Also, the teacher must study the emotional impressions and cognitive characteristics of each child and adapt the teaching process to him. Because "the pedagogical style and quality of the relationship that the teacher builds with gifted students and their parents is often decisive for the development of students' musical abilities" [8]. This creates an opportunity to motivate the students of the specialized school, to master the subjects of science, and, most importantly, to understand their own talent. In this case, "the nature of pedagogical activity requires the manifestation of qualities that contribute to interpersonal interaction by constantly placing teachers in communicative situations" [9].

"The musical pedagogical process has its own laws, forms, stages, styles, general and special, individual and collective, theoretical and practical, concert and independent classes" [10]. In order to clarify the laws of the musical pedagogical process, it is necessary to analyze all the

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connections in the educational process. In this, mental activity, creativity and the processes of encouraging him take an important place.

American psychologist Dj.Ranzulli is a scientist who contributed to the development of world psychology with his influential "Three-nation model of talent". His theory includes cognitive and a number of other factors based on many empirical materials and develops a composite concept of talent. Dj.Ranzulli's main ideas on talent are characterized by his recognition that "Talented and talented children are children who have these characteristics or are able to develop and implement them in any useful activity" [11].

Figure 1: Dj. Ranzulli "The three-nation model of talent"

Dj.Ranzulli's teaching, we can see three main combinations that emphasize the universal nature of talent. These include intellectual abilities (above average), creativity (creative activity), motivation for a specific task.

In the course of education, students' interest in subjects and intellectual abilities are manifested in various forms. A cognitive approach and creativity of students are necessary to develop students' talents through their intellectual abilities, especially in specialized school education.

So, it is confirmed in science that these qualities should be taken into account in the development of students' musical talent. Because "the nature of pedagogical activity constantly puts teachers in communicative situations, which requires the manifestation of qualities that contribute to effective interpersonal interaction" [9]. These are a component of the development of musical talent, through which musical ideas can be expressed and perceived in an aesthetically beautiful and meaningful way. Psychodiagnostically, this allows to determine the level of mastering of basic speech and thinking operations on musical material to determine whether the subject can be an active creator of musical beauty" [12].

The development of students' musical talent in the conditions of economic education is the result of the interaction of the quality and nature of the activity, the interaction of the social and cultural environment. Also, the psychological mechanisms of self-development are of great importance in the formation of individual talent and the realization of the child's creative activity. The continuity of this mechanism is based on special models and concepts used in talent development.

Conclusion: Basically, the development of human society is a process related to the emergence of new talents. The reason is that with the lofty ideas of such talented people, it is possible not only to achieve the progress of science, but also to see the

positive aspects of society and the thinking of people living in it. In order to further develop this mechanism in accordance with the needs of the times, it is necessary to discover new talents, educate them, increase their literacy, correctly identify and direct the direction of talent, and use talent for the development of our country.

Currently, there is a growing need for mentally developed, talented, young personnel who are able to implement progressive changes and are able to promote their ideas. Because science and production cannot develop without new ideas, but they cannot be developed intentionally. So, the realization of this goal is likely to happen through economic changes in social life, the need to form a highly educated creative person of the society. This has a special place with the need to actively influence the development of the country and increase its competitiveness, and the formation of a talented person.

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